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Research Article

RISK FACTORS OF LOW BIRTH WEIGHT INFANTS ADMITTED IN SHEIKH ZAYED HOSPITAL RAHIM YAR KHAN

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Abstract:

Background: Low birth weight (LBW) is a preventable public health problem particularly prevalent in developing countries. Up to 25% of neonates in Pakistan are classed as LBW. There are numerous factors contributing to LBW, both maternal and fetal. The maternal risk factors are biologically and socially interrelated; most are however, modifiable.

Objective: the objective of this study was to enlist the risk factors of low birth weight among low birth weight children admitted pediatric ward of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan

Methodology: Study design: Cross sectional study. Setting: This was conducted in pediatric ward, Gynecology & obstetrics ward of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan. Duration: This study was conducted from 5th -25th January 2015. Sampling technique: Convenient sampling technique; with all the consecutive low birth weight babies, admitted in pediatric ward, during study period, were included. Data collection: mothers of 56 low birth weight babies admitted in pediatrics ward were interviewed. The data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 16.

Results: Mean age of mothers was 25+5 years; mean family income 14687+16000, weight of newborn, 1.8+0.4 kg. It was found that 94% babies were premature, 59% mothers were illiterate; 36% fathers were illiterate. 75% belonged to rural areas. 32% mothers were hypertensive and 59% anemic. We found that 48% had drug history and 64% belonged to Saraiki ethnicity.

Conclusion: This study enlisted prematurely, low maternal and paternal education, maternal anemia, less duration birth spacing, rural residence, long distance from health facility were main risk factors among low birth weight babies in pediatric ward of a tertiary care hospital.

Key Words: low birth weight, risk factors, prematurely.

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INTRODUCTION:

Low birth weight (LBW) is a multifactorial phenomenon defined as a birth weight less than 2500 g. remains a significant public health problem in many parts of the world and is associated with a range of both short- and long-term adverse consequences. Babies with a birth weight of less than 2500 g. irrespective of the period of their gestation are termed as Low birth weight (LBW) babies. Low birth weight (LBW) is potentially preventable public health problem particularly prevalent in developing countries. It contributes substantially to neonatal, infant and childhood mortality as well as to morbidity. In addition, the weight of an infant of birth is an important indicator of maternal health and nutrition prior to and during pregnancy.

Low birth weight as defined by WHO: A birth weight less than 2500 g (before 1976, the WHO definition was less than or equal to 2500 g). since below this value birth-weight-specific infant mortality begins to rise rapidly. However, plots of the cumulative frequency distribution of birth weight show two different normal distributions and 2000 g has been suggested as a lower cut-off point.

The overall public health importance of LBW is determined not only by the risks for subsequent morbidity and mortality, but also by how frequently it occurs, its prevalence in a given population. The best available global estimates of mean birth weight and the prevalence of LBW were produced by WHO in 1979 and update to 1982. of the 127 million infants born in the world in 1982, 20 million (16%) were estimated to weigh less than 2500 g, and over 90% of these countries but also of their much higher prevalence of LBW. The lowest birth weights were reported for Asia, with mean values ranging from about 2700-2800 g in the Indian subcontinent to 3200-3300 g in Chinnad Japan, and corresponding LBW rates of 30-40% and 5-6%, respectively. In west in North Africa, the corresponding values were 3200-3300 and 5-15%. Teenage of mean birth weights was 2900-3100 g within LBW rate of 10-18% in Central America and, respectively, 3100-300 g and 9-12 % in South America.

The highest rates are in South Asia and the lowest in East Asia. In East Asia, the proportion of LBW ranges from 10%, to 10%, with the exception of Thailand, where an estimated 36% of all infants are LBW. In South Asia, the problem is acuter with up to 50% of all neonates having LBW. Up to 25% of neonates in Pakistan are classed as LBW. Infants with LBW have higher rates of morbidity and mortality from infectious disease, rates of morbidity

and mortality from infectious disease, malnutrition and growth failure and are also more likely to have abnormal cognitive development. Neurological impairment and poor school performance. These babies are at greater risk of cardiovascular disease, hypertension and diabetes in adult life. There are numerous factors contributing to LBW, both maternal and fetal. The maternal risk factors are biologically and socially interrelated; most are, however, modifiable.

In Pakistan, statistics are available, national nutrition surveys are carried out and the prevalence of LBW has been estimated at 12%-25%, there has, however, been very little research done on risk factors of LBW among women aged 15-35 years.

Low birth (LBW) is a major determinant of infant mortality and morbidity is an important indicator of reproductive health and general health status of population. LBW is considered the single most important predictor of infant mortality, especially of deaths within the first month of life. It continues to remain a major public health problem worldwide especially in the developing countries. Across the world, neonatal mortality is 20 times more likely for LBW babies compared to heavier babies (= 2.5kg) Birth weight is the single most important criterion for deterring the neonatal and infant survival. In both developed and developing countries, birth weight is probably the single most important factors that affects neonatal mortality, in addition to being a significant determination of post-neonatal infant mortality and of infant and childhood morbidity.

Thus, birth weight has long been a subject of clinical and epidemiological investigations and a target for public health intervention. In particular, considerable attention has been focused on the causal determinants of birth weight, and especially of low birth weight (LBW) in order to identify potentially modifiable factors.

Rationale of study: Pakistan has high infant mortality and morbidity indicators. The underlying causes may be from diverse background reasons. Low birth weight is one of these factors leading to high mortality among children. So current study was planned to enlist the underlying causes of low birth weight in our study setting. With the aim to suggest intervention to control this condition among new born.

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of this study was to: Enlist the risk factors of low birth weight among newborns admitted

in pediatric ward of Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan.

METHODOLOGY:

Study desing: Cross sectional study.

Study site: This was conducted in pediatric ward, Gynecology & obsetrics ward of Sheikh Zayed Hospital.

Study duration: The study was conducted from 5-25 Jan 2015.

Study subjects: Low birth weight (less than 2500 gm) children admitted after birth in pediatric ward.

Sample size: Sample size is total of 56 children of 56 children of low birth weight who were admitted in pediatric ward during study period.

Sampling technique: Convenient sampling technique, with all the consecutive low birth weight babies, admitted in pediatric ward during study period, were included.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Low birth weight (less than 2500 gm of weight) of either sex.
2. Low birth weight babies admitted on date of delivery.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Mother not willing to participate
2. Mother not present at the time of data collection.

Data Collection: Data was collected from mothers of low birth weight babies after getting informed verbal consent. The study variables included age of mother, gravida, parity, duration of gestation, mother education, father education, family income, drug history, no. of children. Previous mode of delivery, no. of antenatal visits, distance from near health center, anemia.

Data analysis: The data was entered in SPSS version 16 numerical variables like age, no. of children monthly family income, and no. of antenatal visits were presented as Mean + Standard deviation, whereas qualitative variables like anemia, mode of delivery, education were presented as percentages.

RESULTS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted to enlist risk factors of low birth weight.

Table I: Age of Mothers (N=56)

Characteristic	Age (years)
Mean	26
Median	25
Mode	30
Standard deviation	5

Table I shows that Mean age of mothers was 25+5 years.

Table II: Family Income (N=56)

Characteristic	Family income
Mean	14687.5
Median	10000
Mode	5000
Standard deviation	16873

Table II shows that mean family income was 14687+16000 Rs, median was 10000 Rs.

Table III: Age of Mothers at marriage (N=56)

Characteristic	Age at marriage
Mean	20
Median	19
Mode	18
Standard deviation	5

Table III shows that mean age of mother at marriage was 20+5 years.

Table IV: Gravida (N=56)

Characteristic	Gravida
Mean	2
Median	2
Mode	1
Standard deviation	1

Table IV shows that mean gravida was 2+1

Table V: Number of children (N=56)

Characteristic	No of children
Mean	2
Median	2
Mode	1
Standard deviation	1

Table V shows that men number of children was 2+1.

Table VI: Time since last child (N=56)

Characteristic	Timesince previous child
Mean	2
Median	2
Mode	1
Standard deviation	1

Table VI shows that mean time since last child birth was (years) 2+1.

Table VII: Age of new born (N=56)

Characteristic	Weight (kg)
Mean	1.8
Median	2
Mode	2
Standard deviation	0.4

Table VII shows mean weight of newborn was 1.8+0.4 kg.

Table VIII: Years since marriage (N=56)

Characteristic	Year since marriage
Mean	6
Median	5
Mode	1
Standard deviation	4

Table VIII shows that men years since marriage was 5+4 years.

Table IX: duration of pregnancy (N=56)

Characteristic	Duration
Mean	34
Median	34
Mode	36
Standard deviation	3

Table IX shows that mean duration of pregnancy was 34+3 weeks.

Table X: Number of antenatal visits (N=56)

Characteristic	No of antenatal visits
Mean	4
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard deviation	3

Table X shows that mean number of antenatal visits was 4+3

Table XI: Distance from nearest health facility (N=56)

Characteristic	No of antenatal visits
Mean	4
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard deviation	3

Table XI shows that mean distance from nearest health facility (km) was 31+34 and median was 20 km.

Table XII: Education of mother

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	33	58.9
Primary	13	23.2
Matric	5	8.9
Graduate or above	5	8.9
Total	56	100.0

Table XII shows that 58.9% mothers were illiterate.

Table XIII: Education of fathers

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	20	35.7
Primary	11	19.6
Matric	18	32.1
Graduate or above	7	12.5
Total	56	100.0

Table XIII shows that 35.7% father were illiterate.

Table XIV: Gender of child

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	20	50
Female	28	50
Total	56	100

Table XIV shows that in the study, male and female ratio was found to be 1:1

Table XV: Distribution of Residence

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	42	75
Urban	14	25
Total	56	100

Table XV shows that 75% mothers belonged to rural areas.

Graph I: Residence residence

Graph I show majority of the mothers belonged to rural areas.

Table XVI: Disease distribution of Mothers

Disease	Frequency	Percentage
No disease	31	55.4
Hypertension	18	32
Eclampsia	9	16.07
Pre-eclampsia	6	10.71
Diabetes	3	5.3
IHD	1	1.8
Smoking	1	1.8

Table XVI shows that 32% mothers were hypertensive, 16% suffered from eclampsia whereas 55.4% had no disease.

Table XVII: Drug History

Drugs	Frequency	Percent
Yes	27	48.2
No	29	51.8
Total	56	100.0

Table XVII shows that 48% mothers have had a positive drug history.

Table XVIII: Iron/ Folic Intake

Iron / Folic acid	Frequency	Percent
Yes	41	73.2
No	15	26.8
Total	56	100.0

Table XVIII shows that 73.2% mothers used to take iron and folic acid.

Table XX: Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percent
Saraiki	36	64.3
Punjabi	14	30.4
Sindhhi	3	5.4
Total	56	100

Table XX shows that 64.3% mothers belonged to Saraiki ethnicity.

Table XXI: Birth of Child

	Frequency	Percent
Normal delivery	30	53.6
C-section	26	46.4
Total	56	100

Table XXI shows that 53.6% were normally delivered.

Table XXII: Anemia in Mothers

Anemia	Frequency	Percent
Yes	33	58.9
No	23	41.1
Total	56	100

Table XXII shows that 58.9 % mothers were anemic.

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted to enlist risk factor of low birth weight among children admitted in pediatrics ward of sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan. Our study showed that, mean age of mothers was 25 ± 5 years mean family income was 14687 ± 16000 Rs, median was 10000 Rs, age at marriage was 20 ± 5 years gravida was 2 ± 1 , number of children 2 ± 1 , time since last child birth (years) 2 ± 1 , weight of newborn, 1.8 ± 0.4 kg, years since marriage, 5 ± 4 duration of pregnancy was 33 ± 3 weeks, number of antenatal visit, 4 ± 3 and distance from nearest health facility (km), 31 ± 34 , median was 20 km. However a previous study reported, birth spacing <36 months, maternal height 145 cm pre-delivery weight of 55 kg, pregnancy weight gain of 6kg, exposure to tobacco, inadequate antenatal care, maternal hypertension, low socio-economics status, maternal anemia and less maternal education were associated with delivery of a low birth weight infants. They reported risk factors as; birth spacing in months, 26.42 (4.56), mother age(years) 23.19 (3.37), parity 1,61.3% anemia 52.2% hypertension, 23.4% Inadequate ANC, 62.4% below poverty line 47.4% tobacco exposure, 26.6% maternal illiteracy, 27% and paternal 20.6% However, in contrast, as far as education is concerned, our study showed that 58.9% mothers were illiterate and 35% fathers were illiterate.

In a previous study overall mean birth weight was found to be 2.64 ± 0.444 with 95% confidence interval of 2.59-2.69. This is in contrast to our study where mean new born weight was 1.8 ± 0.4 kg. in their study, primigravida mother showed the highest prevalence of low birth weight (30.86%), $p < 0.001$). the main factors which were significantly associated with LBW were maternal education, stature, age at delivery; short inter pregnancy interval, inadequate antenatal care, and per capita income of family.

In our study male and female ration of newborn was found to be 1:1 but in a previous study it was found that proportion of LBW was 32.59% in males and 36.37% in females, however this difference was not found to be statistically significant.

Our study showed that 75% mothers belonged to rural areas. This is also shown in a previous study which reported that contextual-level factors were significantly associated with LBW: being a rural dweller increased the likelihood of having a LBW infant by 43% while living in poverty-concentrated communities increased the risk of having a LBW infant twofold. In neighborhoods with a high coverage of safe water supply the odds of having a LBW infant reduced by 28%.

Our study showed that 32% mothers are hypertensive, 1.8% mothers were smokers while in a previous study reported hypertension in 23.4% mothers and tobacco exposure in 26.6% mothers. In our study DHQ was the nearest health center for 44.6% people however they reported 62.4% mothers had inadequate antenatal care.

Our study reported that 73.2% mothers used to take iron and folic acid. And 78.6% LBW babies were delivered by doctors however a previous study reported antenatal care provided by doctor of 83.6% mothers and daily iron intake of 67.1% mothers.

Our study showed that 53.6% LBW babies were normally delivered. This is also consistent with a previous study which showed that 43% were normally delivered.

Our study showed that 94% of the newborn were premature. This is in contrast to a previous study which showed that only 26% newborn were premature. They reported anemia among 12% mothers and a gap of <than 1.5 years among 11% of mothers. However, in our study mean duration of gap was 2+1 years and anemic mothers were 58.9%.

CONCLUSION:

Our study enlisted prematurely, low maternal and paternal education, maternal anemia, less duration of pregnancy, rural residence, long distance from health facility were main risk factors found among low birth weight babies in pediatric ward of a tertiary care hospital.

It is suggested that health education programs should focus on addressing the risk factors found in our area and a larger study with objective of determining the association of risk factors with low birth weight may be conducted.

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